

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT COMBINATION OF DDGS AND AZOLLA BASED DIET ON SERUM BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN BROILER CHICKENS

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to evaluate the effect of different combination of DDGS and Azolla based diet on serum biochemical parameters of broilers chickens. One hundred thirty five Mareks disease vaccinated straight run day-old commercial broiler chicks were equally and randomly distributed into three treatment groups which were subdivided into three replicates containing 15 chicks in each, reared on deep litter system in pens up to 6 weeks of age. The dietary treatment groups were the Control diet without DDGS and Azolla (T0), Broiler ration containing 10 % Replacement of SBM by DDGS (5%) and Azolla Meal (5%) (T1), Broiler ration containing 15 % Replacement of SBM by DDGS (7.5 %) + Azolla Meal (7.5%) (T2). The blood biochemical estimations were carried out at the end of experimental trial. The individual serum samples were analyzed for total protein, albumin, Total lipids –HDL, LDL, Cholesterol and Serum calcium and Serum phosphorus. The results show that the values of total serum protein, albumin, calcium and phosphorus from all the groups were within normal biochemical range. The serum cholesterol, LDL and HDL were significantly reduced in broilers fed T1 and T2 groups. In conclusion, study reveal that combination of DDGS and Azolla based diet do not adversely affect serum biochemical parameters in broiler birds

Keywords: Broiler, DDGS, Azolla, Serum Biochemical Parameter

Introduction

The feed cost account 70-75 percent of total expenditure of the broiler production. Recently, the conventional feed ingredient like Maize and Soybean meal became a fewer availability due to stagnation in maize production, its diversification to starch industry, forward trading in maize and export of soybean meal. Certain serious attempts were made by nutritionists in the past few years to substitute the conventional feed ingredients with animal wastes, slaughterhouse wastes, different non-conventional feed resources, etc (Mishra et al.2016). The Distillers dried grains with solubles (DDGS) are co-product obtained from the dry-milling process for ethanol production, using fermentation with yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). Distillers Dried solubles is the richest source of vitamins, lowest in fiber and highest in fat, yielding approximately 91 % digestible energy value of corn. Corn DDGS generally contains approximately 27% of crude protein, 10% of fat, 0.8% of P and 0.7% of S and they are suitable feed for both cattle and poultry (Leaflet, et al., 2008). The crude protein in DDGS is of high quality because it includes yeast protein, The earlier workers replacement of SBM by DDGS has indicated that DDGS at higher levels in chicken diet had either non-significant or negative effect on growth, feed efficiency or carcass characteristics in chicks, and while the optimum levels of substitution differed in different experiments (Lukasiewicz, et al., 2012 Mishra et al. 2016).

Azolla is an aquatic fern freely floating on water surface of small ponds. it is very rich in proteins, vitamins (vitamin A, vitamin B12 and Beta-Carotene), essential amino acids, and minerals like calcium, phosphorous, potassium, ferrous, copper, magnesium etc. On a dry weight basis, it contains 25 - 35 percent protein, 10 - 15 percent minerals and 7 - 10 percent of amino acids, bio-active substances and bio-polymers (Parthasarathy, et al., 2001). Azolla is one of the plant resources with high biomass and protein production. Azolla pinnata was used as feedstuff in broiler chicken (Querubin, et al., 1986; Parthasarathy, et al., 2002). Considering the promising and competitive nutrient composition of DDGS and Azolla with conventional soybean

meal an effort was made to reduce the cost of feeding without altering the growth performance., the present investigation was studied to evaluate the combine effect of feeding distillers dried grain with solubles (DDGS) and Azolla on serum biochemical parameter in broiler chicken.

Material And Methods

One hundred thirty five day old broiler straightrun chicks of “Vencobb” strain were purchased from private hatchery. The chicks were equally and randomly distributed in to three treatment groups. Each treatment groups were further divided in to three replicates with fifteen chicks in each replicate. The dietary treatment groups were the Control diet (T0), Broiler ration containing 10 % Replacement of SBM by DDGS (5%) and Azolla Meal (5%) (T1), Broiler ration containing 15 % Replacement of SBM by DDGS (7.5 %) + Azolla Meal (7.5%) (T2). These chicks were reared on deep litter system in pens up to 6 weeks of age. The feed was provided as per treatment and water was provided ad-lib to all the treatment groups throughout the experimental period. The broiler pre starter feed was provided up to seven days, later on broiler starter and broiler finisher feed were provided from second to third and fourth to six weeks of age respectively. The blood biochemical estimations were carried out at the end of experimental trial. The blood samples were collected from wing vein into tubes without any anticoagulant for separation of serum. The serum samples were maintained at -20 °C until analyzed. The individual serum samples were analyzed for total protein, albumin, Total lipids –HDL, LDL, Cholesterol and Serum calcium, and Serum phosphorus. The biochemical estimations were done by using Automatic Biochemical Analyzer ‘3000 revolution’ made by Tulip’s Diagnostic Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. The methodology and the set of reagents used in respect of each parameter were as per the recommendations of the manufacturer of the analyzer system. The data obtained on various parameters studied during this experimental trial were subjected to statistical analysis as described by Snedecor, and Cochran, (1994).

Results And Discussion**Table1. Influence of dietary supplementation of DDGS and Azolla on serum biochemical constituents of broilers at 6 wks of age**

Parameters	Treatments		
	T0	T1	T2
Total Protein (g/dl)	3.72±0.14	3.89±0.12	3.93±0.08

Albumin (g/dl)	1.62±0.01	1.65±0.03	1.66±0.01
Serum cholesterol (mg/dl)	150.23±1.17 ^a	141.48±1.84 ^b	138.89±1.73 ^b
Serum LDL(mg/dl)	63.34±0.97 ^a	55.78±0.74 ^b	52.59±1.45 ^c
Serum HDL(mg/dl)	62.10±1.09 ^a	56.14±1.11 ^b	52.93±1.46 ^c
Serum Calcium (mg/dl)	9.44±0.29	9.79±0.27	9.53±0.25
Serum Phosphorus (mg/dl)	5.26±0.44	5.40±0.42	5.11±0.37

Total Serum Protein (g/dl)

The values of total serum protein were found statically non significant ($p>0.05$). The values of total serum protein from all the groups were absolutely within normal biochemical range with comparatively higher values in group T₂ followed by T₁ and T₀. Similar findings were reported by Kaya and Tarkan (2013) with no significant variation and no adverse effects on total serum protein after replacement of soy meal with DDGS upto 15% level. Similar findings were also reported by Gacche (2013) with non significant variation among the groups with no adverse effect on total serum protein after replacement of soy meal by DDGS upto 20% level. However, non significantly higher values of total serum protein were observed at 30% level of replacement. Further, Magre (2012) reported that feeding of Azolla at 0, 2.5, 5 and 7.5 in broiler ration with replacement of soy meal do not significantly and adversely affected total serum protein of broiler birds. The present study confirms that equal combination of DDGS and Azolla at 10% and 15% level by replacing soybean meal do not adversely affect serum total protein content.

Serum Albumin

The average values of serum albumin (g/dl) observed were 1.62±0.01, 1.65±0.03 and 1.66±0.01 in control group T₀, treatment group T₁ and T₂ respectively. No statistical significant variation ($p>0.05$) was observed among the groups. The values of total serum albumin from all the groups were absolutely within normal biochemical range with comparatively higher values in group T₂ followed by T₁ and T₀. Similar findings were reported by Gacche (2013) with non significant values of serum albumin among the treatment groups fed upto 30% DDGS and control group with 0% DDGS in replacement of soybean meal. Further, Magre (2012) reported that replacement of soybean meal with Azolla meal maximum upto 7.5% do not adversely affect serum albumin value. It was also observed that there was no significant difference in serum albumin values of broiler birds fed maximum upto 7.5% azolla meal and control group fed with soy meal. Present study confirms that the equal combination of DDGS and Azolla meal at 10% and 15% level do not adversely affect the serum albumin levels.

Serum Cholesterol

The significantly lower ($p<0.01$) cholesterol levels were recorded in T₂ followed by T₁ as compare to T₀. The values of total cholesterol observed in control group T₀ and Treatment group T₁ and T₂ were absolutely within normal biochemical range. Gacche (2013) reported that feeding of DDGS upto 30% level in replacement of soybean meal significantly reduced total cholesterol level in broiler chickens. Similar findings were reported in laying ducks by Awad *et al.* (2011) with reduced total cholesterol level up to 20% in group fed with 30% DDGS as compare to control. However, Kaya and Tarkan (2013) reported that inclusion of DDGS at 5, 10 and 15% level significantly reduced serum cholesterol levels. Further, Balaji *et al.* (2010) reported that significantly reduced total cholesterol levels were observed after inclusion of Azolla meal at 3 and 4.5% levels in replacement of soybean meal. Magre (2012) observed similar findings with significantly reduced cholesterol levels in the groups fed Azolla meal either at 5% or 7.5% level in replacement of soybean meal. The present study confirms that the inclusion of equal combination of DDGS and Azolla at 10% and 15% level in replacement of soybean meal significantly reduced total cholesterol level in broiler chickens

Serum LDL

The significantly lowest ($p<0.01$) LDL cholesterol was observed in treatment group T₂ (52.59±1.45) followed by T₁ (55.78±0.74) and significantly higher values were observed in control group T₀ (63.34±0.97). It was also recorded that all three experimental groups have shown significantly different LDL values. It was reported that inclusion of Azolla meal up to 7.5% level in replacement of soybean meal had significantly reduced serum LDL values of broiler birds (Magre, 2012).

Serum HDL

The average value of serum HDL (mg/dl) observed were 62.10±1.09, 56.14±1.11 and 52.93±1.46 in control group T₀, treatment group T₁ and T₂ respectively. Among the experimental groups significantly lower ($p<0.05$) serum HDL was observed in treatment group T₂ (52.93±1.46) followed by treatment group T₁ (56.14±1.11) and higher in control group T₀ (62.10±1.09). It was also observed that all three treatment groups were significantly different ($p<0.05$) from each other. However, Magre (2012) reported significantly higher values of serum HDL in broiler birds after inclusion of Azolla meal up to 7.5% in replacement of soy meal.

Calcium

The average values of serum calcium (mg/dl) observed were 9.44±0.29, 9.79±0.27 and 9.53±0.25 in control group T₀, treatment group T₁ and T₂ respectively. The values of serum calcium recorded in all three experimental groups were found statistically non significant ($p>0.05$). Further, it was also noted that the values of serum calcium were absolutely within normal biochemical range. It can be mentioned that replacement of soybean meal with equal combination of DDGS and Azolla meal at 10% or 15% level do not adversely affect serum calcium levels of broiler birds

Phosphorus

The average values of serum phosphorus (mg/dl) observed were 5.26±0.44, 5.40±0.42 and 5.11±0.37 in control group T₀, treatment group T₁ and T₂ respectively. It was observed that values of serum phosphorus were found statistically non significant ($p>0.05$) from each other. It was also recorded that values of serum phosphorus were absolutely within normal biochemical range. It can be mentioned that addition of equal combination of DDGS and Azolla meal at 10% and 15% level by replacing soybean meal do not adversely affect serum phosphorus level in broiler birds.

Conclusions

The addition of equal combination of DDGS and Azolla meal at 10% and 15% level by replacing soybean meal do not adversely affect serum biochemical parameters in broiler birds.

References

1. Awad, A. L., Hussein, M. A. A., Ghonim, A. I. A., & Kasim, M. G. (2011). Effect of dietary inclusion level of distillers dried grains with solubles on laying performance in Domyati ducks. *Egyptian Poultry Science Journal*, 31(1), 51-63.
2. A.K. Verma¹, P. S. Pramanik¹, M. K. Verma², Jaswant Singh², Ruma Devi³, A.K. Srivastav² Andgaurav Panday¹ 2021, Effect Of Moringa Oleifera Leaf Extracts On Carcass Characteristics And Mortality Of Broiler Chickens, Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxx, Oct 2021 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 20-22.

3. **Balaji, K., Jalaludeen, A., & Kannan, A. (2010).** Effect of dietary Azolla on cholesterol content in broiler chicken. *Indian Veterinary Journal*, **87**(5), 478-480.
4. **Gacche, S. M.(2013).** Utilization of Distillers Dried Grains with Solubles in Broilers Chicken Diet. *M.V.Sc. Thesis submitted to Maharashtra Animal and Fishery Sciences University, Nagpur.*
5. **G. K. Singh, D. Niyogi* , K.K. Tripathi, N. Joshi1 2018, A. Vaish And Abhishek Mishra, Pathomorphological Changes In Broiler Chickens Due To Spontaneous E. Coli Infection, Vol. Viii, Issue Special(A) , August 2018 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 348-353.**
6. **Gaurav Panday1 , P S Pramanik2 , P K Chaudhary3 , Amit Tiwari4 A K Verma5 , K D Singh5 , Jaswant Singh6 , Mukesh Kumar7, 2019,** Effect Of Neem Leaves Feeding On Serum Biochemical Parameters Of Commercial Broiler Chickens, Vol. Viii, Special Issue, National Seminar On Rttepsr Nduat Ayodhya-2019 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 53-55.
7. **Kaya, K and S Tarkan (2013).** Effects of Different Levels Distillers Dried Grains with Solubles on Growth Performance, Carcass Quality and Some Blood Parameters in Broilers, *Kafkas Univ Vet Fak Derg*, **19** (1): 161-166, 2013
8. **Leaflet, A. S. (2008)** Maximum Dietary Content of Corn Dried Distiller's Grains with Solubles in Diets for Laying Hens. Effects on Nitrogen Balance, Manure Excretion, Egg production, and Egg Quality. *Animal Industry Report 2008*, Iowa State University, Available from: <http://www.ddgs.umn.edu>
9. **Lukasiewicz, M., Pietrzak, D., Niemiec, J., Mroczek, J. and Michalczak, M.(2012).** Application of DDGS as a replacer of soybean meal in broiler chicken feeding. *Archiv Tierzucht*, **55**: 496-505.
10. **Magre A.R. (2012).** Effect of feeding azolla (*Azolla pinnata*) on performance and blood biochemical profile of broilers. *M.V.Sc. Thesis submitted to Maharashtra Animal and Fishery Sciences University, Nagpur.*
11. **Mishra, D. B., Roy, D., Kumar, V., Bhattacharyya, A., Kumar, M., Kushwaha, R., & Vaswani, S. (2016).** Effect of feeding azolla (*Azolla pinnata*) meal on the performance, nutrient utilization and carcass characteristics of Chabro chicken. *Indian Journal of Poultry Science*, **51**(3), 259-263.
12. **Parthasarathy, R., Kadirvel, R. and Kathaperumal, V. (2001)** Chemical evaluation of Azolla as a poultry feed ingredient. *Cheiron*, **30**: 35-37.
13. **Parthasarathy, R., Kadirvel, R. and Kathaperumal, V. 2002.** Azolla as a partial replacement for fishmeal in broiler rations. *Indian Veterinary Journal*, **79** (2): 144-146.
14. **Querubin, L. J., Alcantara, P. F. and Princesa, A. O. (1986).** Chemical composition of three Azolla species (*A. caroliniana*, *A. microphylla* and *A. pinnata*) and feeding value of Azolla meal (*A. microphylla*) in broiler ration. *Philippine Agriculturist*, **69**: 479-490
15. **Snedecor, G. M. and Cochran, G. W. 1994.** Statistical methods (8th edition). Affiliated East West Press. Iowa State University Press, USA. *Published by Oxford and IBN Publishing Co. Kolkata-16.*